

USING A COMMUNICATION NETWORK IN STUDYING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the use of a communication network in studying the Russian language in non-linguistic universities.

The Internet in the modern world is considered one of the main sources of educational information and performs the most important functions of a channel of written communication. From the point of view of language teaching, the Internet can be considered as a teaching tool, as a source of educational materials, as an opportunity to create new educational materials, and as a mechanism for organizing intercultural communication.

In the policy documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, at a meeting of the Board of Trustees of the Uzbekistan Foundation, it was noted that "raising a healthy and harmoniously developed generation means building the foundation of a state with a great future, gaining high authority in the world." This can be achieved, in our opinion, by fluently speaking languages, in our time especially the Russian language. If in the previous decades of the twentieth century the circle of people who had the need to communicate in Russian was quite narrow, now the situation has changed.

Communication and technological transformations in society have involved both direct and indirect communication (for example, through the Internet) quite a large number of people of various professions, ages and interests. Accordingly, the need for the use of the Russian language has increased. Language teaching as a means of communication and generalization of spiritual heritage has acquired priority importance. On the threshold of the new century, the sociocultural context of language learning, especially Russian, has changed significantly. Agreeing with E.I. Passov, who calls for the formation of a "spiritual person" in the process of studying a foreign language culture (Russian language), one cannot but admit that the Russian language, of course, provides us with all the opportunities for raising such a person. In this regard, the concept of "linguistic personality" is not reduced to mastery of the language system, knowledge of linguistic rules and categories, which is still the case in Russian language classes.

Language becomes part of social memory, a set of meanings that form the orienting basis of not only speech activity, but also other activities, for example, cognitive, since speech by its nature is a “non-instinctive, acquired,” “cultural” function. Thus, the educational and self-educational functions of the Russian language, their professional significance at school, at university, and in the labor market as a whole have increased significantly, which has entailed increased motivation for communication. In the practice of working in educational institutions, the pressing problem of the day is the education of a socially active person who is capable of taking responsibility for independently made decisions. For graduates of educational institutions, the requirements of readiness for orientation in a life saturated with information flows and for continuous self-learning have become mandatory.

The use of a communication network in studying Russian as a foreign language for students of our universities is the norm today. In this regard, the use and improvement of methods of the educational process and educational technologies is of particular importance. This is especially true in the field of studying Russian as a foreign language, where interaction with the teacher in the classroom cannot be effective without students independently mastering the necessary vocabulary. And also, in parallel, you can use the linguoculturological approach when teaching Russian as a foreign language, which is the basis for the formation of a linguistic personality, which, from our point of view, presupposes not only a dialogue with ethnic cultures, but also the familiarization of the individual with human culture, and in its components - professional, environmental, informational, etc.

Research into the real state of the problem in the theory and practice of teaching Russian as a foreign language in schools, academic lyceums, vocational colleges and universities has revealed: an insufficient level of development of theoretical and methodological approaches to the implementation of socialization of the individual in the modern information society on the basis of effective language proficiency using the latest information technology and therefore the use of listening is relevant in teaching methods.

Listening skills can become stable if the student independently improves them in his free time. This can be facilitated by means of information and communication technologies, which allow you to hear the speech of native Russian speakers, see educational information via a computer, provide immediate feedback between the student and the learning tool, as well as organize educational activities at an individual pace and monitor the results of assimilation. The success of students' acquisition of Russian as a foreign language is determined by many objective and subjective factors, among which the degree of development of students' psychological listening mechanisms is of particular importance; awareness of one's own language learning goals. At the same time, based on the linguoculturological approach and equating the process of formation of a linguistic personality with the process of socialization of the individual, we expand the concept of a linguistic personality, understanding by a linguistic personality not just any native speaker capable of producing speech works in a given language, or a typical representative of a given linguistic community.

Thus, the most difficult type of speech activity, especially for students for whom Russian is not their native language, therefore, work on developing the skill of perceiving speech by ear requires painstaking efforts. In this regard, the approach of foreign psychologists and methodologists to listening, which is based on a comparison of the mechanisms (listening) of native speakers and learners of a new language, attracts attention. A child immediately

becomes a listener as soon as he is born, but after only months he begins to speak, and he will learn to read and write only after a few years. This means that auditing skills are primary and form the basis for the formation of all other speech skills and abilities. This leads to the fact that for a student of the Russian language, both the process of special training in listening, acquired during training and improved independently, and the need to know one's natural abilities for self-learning to understand foreign language speech by ear, in this case the Russian language, are important. For example, dialogues are the result of semantic processing of audio information, which generates the student's communicative intention and logic of thought.

Thus, in the process of studying Russian as a foreign language, students not only comprehend the way of expressing thoughts, but also perceive the language as a source of information about the national culture of the people, since language is a sign of the nation, expresses the national culture of the people who speak it. And also, it becomes the basis for the intellectual development and self-development of the individual, the basis for the formation of his readiness for productive activity in society, since it equips the individual with a tool for acquiring knowledge in any sphere of education and social order, allows a person to know himself, master the means of self-analysis, self-expression and self-realization in society. Problems of socialization of the individual in the education system are of great importance for effectively solving the problems of upbringing, training and development of the younger generation.

The concept of "personal socialization," on the one hand, has been narrowed to its interpretation from the point of view of effective mastery of language as a mechanism for inscribing a person into the system of being, mainly through that part of a person's conceptual world that is "linked" to language and is refracted through linguistic forms. On the other hand, there is a significant expansion, even globalization, of the interpretation of the concept of "socialization of the individual." Due to the system-forming nature and multifunctionality of the language itself, with the help of which knowledge is integrated, consciousness is formed as a human property, abstract thinking and memory are developed, general intellectual development is ensured, etc.

It should be especially emphasized that, interpreting the Russian language as the main means of socialization of the individual in a modern information and humanitarian society, we consider informatization and humanitarization in continuous unity, understanding by informatization of society humanitarian aspects in the broad sense of the development of computer science and electronic computing technology: philosophical, sociocultural, ideological, ideological, methodological, etc.

In the XXI century, the study of Russian languages in the CIS countries is intended to "socialize" the individual by developing the ability to freely navigate the flow of information, filter the main thing through the prism of universal human values and the mentality of students, independently determine the directions and boundaries of searching for the necessary information, be fluent in methods and means of management and transmission of information through the teacher.

In the modern world, the changing requirements and need for studying the Russian language have determined new methods and goals of teaching in secondary schools, academic lyceums, vocational colleges and higher educational institutions, aimed at developing the student's personality - active, proactive, enterprising, active, highly cultural; a patriot with a developed

gift of humanity and non-standard creative thinking, capable of fully living and working successfully in the conditions of a modern information society, in a market and democracy, urgently require new content of education (including, and above all, in the Russian language, which occupies one of the leading places in educational and educational system), new teaching aids, methods and technologies, the fundamental principles of which, in our opinion, should be an authorized, integrative, activity and automated approach to training, education and development.

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